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1. INTRODUCTION

This handbook presents the guidelines developed merging the redesign actions from D6000-A and the needs identified from the stakeholders' survey process conducted as part of WP6000 and here highlighted, which aimed to gather scientific and industrial feedback on the topics addressed by the RESIST project. The methodology employed, which combines scientific rigor with expert input from practitioners in the field, represents an innovative approach in the context of current research. In literature, the practice of defining guidelines based on scientific foundations, while simultaneously incorporating expert opinions from both academia and industry, is relatively new. This hybrid approach aims to create a more holistic and practical framework to reach the project's goals. The following sections of the handbook detail the survey process and questions, analyze the responses, and compare the findings with the redesign actions, highlighting the conclusive RESIST guidelines, which also include the methodology and some open access data and KPI of the project.

2. STAKEHOLDERS SURVEY

The survey was designed to analyze the interest of scientific and industrial stakeholders and practitioners to the topic of resilience, with questions based on the technologies employed and the core objectives of the study. These questions not only focus on the theoretical, technical and technological aspects of the project but also engage with broader sectorial perspectives to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the topic at hand.

The survey was distributed to a carefully selected sample through a stratified sampling approach, ensuring representation across different professional roles and sectors. For instance, within the academic world, the sample included three different groups such as professors, researchers, and students, while in industry, it covered various sectors like logistics, manufacturing, and consulting. This stratification allows for a nuanced analysis of the data, reflecting the diverse viewpoints and experiences of individuals within various contexts. The sample is considered a representative subset of the broader population of practitioners, allowing for generalizable conclusions to be drawn within the scope of the project.

Each project partner was responsible for contacting participants within their respective networks via e-mail, ensuring a diverse yet targeted sample of experts. This collaborative, network-based recruitment approach is designed to incorporate insights from a wide range of stakeholders, enhancing the validity of the findings.

The survey questions are listed here alongside their corresponding types, possible introductory statements and other relevant details. If not stated differently, all the questions are mandatory to answer.

2.1. Survey introduction (Section 1)

RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats is a project developed by the research team composed of Sapienza University of Rome, Università Politecnica delle Marche and Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna.

The aim of the project is to quantify and improve resilience parameters in industrial plants exposed to physical and cyber attacks.

Through the development of a Digital Twin (DT) of the plant-operator/staff system, it is possible to simulate high-risk operating conditions and measure the resilience parameters of the integrated system, thus going on to evaluate improvement actions. For more information you can visit the project website (<https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/resist/home>).

This survey aims to probe the interest, feasibility and usefulness in industry of the topics investigated.

The results of the survey will be used by the research team only for research purposes under the “RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats” project.

2.2. Survey questions: Resilience and digital models (Section 2)

Section introduction: *All questions relate to the industrial context in which you work or with which you have academic research collaborations.*

1. How familiar are you with the concept of resilience? *Scale answer from 1 (Little) to 5 (Much).*
2. What does the concept of resilience applied to the industrial context mean to you? *Drop down answer. Only one option to be selected. The first of the three listed options is the one considered correct in the project.*
 - a. Ability of an industrial system to absorb and adapt to disruptions, quickly maintaining or restoring its operational functions.
 - b. Set of measures to anticipate the occurrence of failures and ensure that a plant never stops.
 - c. Strategy to improve production efficiency by minimizing costs and waste, preventing disruptions.
3. Do you think the use of resilience parameters (i.e., robustness, recovery, redundancy, flexibility, etc.) is useful within the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations? *Scale answer from 1 (Not useful) to 5 (Useful).*

Question introduction: *A Digital Twin (DT) represents a physical resource (object, human, system) in a virtual environment. This digital replica uses real-time data to be able to perform simulations and aid decision making.*

4. Do you think the use of DTs can be an effective method to increase the resilience of industrial plants? *Scale answer from 1 (Not so effective) to 5 (Very effective).*

2.3. Survey questions: Digital models for industrial systems (Section 3)

Section introduction: All questions relate to the industrial context in which you work or with which you have academic research collaborations.

5. Do you already use or would you like to use a digital model of the productive facility/system you operate on or have academic research collaborations with to enhance its performance? *Drop down answer. Only one option to be selected.*
 - a. I already do
 - b. I do not but I would like to implement it
 - c. I do not and I do not have interest in using it
 - d. Not applicable
6. If you use it, what are the main performance and/or KPIs that it analyzes? *Optional. Free-text answer.*
7. How important do you think it is to learn more about methods and tools to protect against attacks on production facilities/systems, including cyber, for the industrial settings in which you work or with which you have academic research collaborations? *Scale answer from 1 (Not so important) to 5 (Very important).*
8. What risks/attacks do you feel are most critical in the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations? *Multiple choice answer.*
 - a. Malware/Ransomware
 - b. DDoS attacks
 - c. Data manipulation
 - d. Fires
 - e. Natural events
 - f. Utility interruption
- 8a. List here any other risks not included in the list: *Optional. Free-text answer.*
9. Considering the most critical risks/attacks you identified in questions 8 and 8a, how much do you think the use of DT can mitigate their impact? *Scale answer from 1 (Little) to 5 (Much).*
10. What risks/attacks have you really faced or are recurring in the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations? *Multiple choice answer.*
 - a. Malware/Ransomware
 - b. DDoS attacks
 - c. Data manipulation
 - d. Fires
 - e. Natural events
 - f. Utility interruption

- g. Those entered manually in step 8a

2.4. Survey questions: Digital models for operators/human resources (Section 4)

Section introduction: *All questions relate to the industrial context in which you work or with which you have academic research collaborations.*

11. Do you think that the implementation of a DT of the human component present on the productive facility/system can have a positive impact in terms of risk reduction (both for the plant and the human component)? *Scale answer from 1 (Low impact) to 5 (High impact).*
12. Do you think it is feasible to track the actions of operators/staff, limited to when engaged in high-risk operations, with a view to developing a digital model (DT) limited to internal use for process (not people) safety/performance analysis? *Scale answer from 1 (Not possible) to 5 (Possible).*

Question introduction: *Motion capture (or mocap) is a technology used to record human body movements and transfer them into digital form. The process involves the use of sensors or cameras that track the movements of a real actor or subject. This data is then processed to digitally represent the behavior of the physical person, from which various types of information (ergonomics, work time, etc.) can then be obtained.*

13. Do you think that “mocap” technologies can be profitably applied within the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations, to track the actions of operators limited to when engaged in high-risk operations, and with purposes limited to internal use for process (not people) safety/performance analyses? *Scale answer from 1 (Little profit) to 5 (Much profit).*
- 13a. List here any alternative technologies to “mocap” that are useful in achieving the same ends as set out in question 13, but which you think are better: *Optional. Free-text answer.*

Question introduction: *Mixed Reality (MR) is a technology that combines elements of the real and virtual worlds, allowing them to interact in real time. Unlike augmented reality, which overlays digital content on top of the real environment, and virtual reality, which creates a fully simulated environment, MR blends both, allowing people to see and interact with digital 3-D objects as if they were present in physical space, using visors or smart glasses with motion sensors.*

14. Regardless of the investment, do you think it is technically feasible to have the possibility of being able to equip operators with MR tools (visors with holograms, smart glasses, etc.) in order to help them, thanks to the information obtainable from such tools, during the execution of potentially high-risk operations? *Scale answer from 1 (Low feasibility) to 5 (High feasibility).*

2.5. Survey questions: RESIST Guidelines (Section 5)

Section introduction: *All questions relate to the RESIST project and more generally to industrial systems resilience.*

Question introduction: *The RESIST project uses the technologies described in the previous sections to produce “guidelines” related to industrial plant resilience and cyber-socio-technical systems modeling.*

15. Would you be interested in “guidelines” that propose resilience metrics for industrial plants, considering humans an integral part of the plant/production system? *Scale answer from 1 (Little) to 5 (Much).*
16. In what form would you like to receive/consult them? *Multiple choice answer.*
- To do list
 - Document saved on cloud
 - Paper manual
 - Infographic
17. What is the main information you would like to find listed within them? *Free-text answer.*

2.6. Survey questions: Feedbacks and suggestions (Section 6)

Section introduction: *Here you can leave a comment about the project itself or other suggestions. Also, if you would like to be aware of the results of the project or be informed about upcoming events, you can leave your e-mail here to receive updates. Thank you!*

18. Feedbacks and suggestions. *Optional. Free-text answer.*
19. E-mail. *Optional. Free-text answer.*
20. Your area of employment. *Drop down answer. Only one option to be selected.*
- University
 - Industry
 - Research center
 - Services
 - Student
21. If employed in the industry or services sectors, please add some further details (i.e. ISIC classification): *Optional. Free-text answer.*

3. SURVEY RESULTS

This section presents an analysis of the survey results, providing a discussion of the findings and drawing insights to support the guidelines definition. Out of approximately 150 practitioners contacted, 22 responded to the survey, resulting in a response rate of about 14.7%.

3.1. Survey answers: Resilience and digital models (Section 2)

1. How familiar are you with the concept of resilience?

Figure 1. Question one results: familiarity with the concept of resilience.

2. What does the concept of resilience applied to the industrial context mean to you?

Figure 2. Question two results: resilience definition in the industrial context.

The first two questions aim to assess the respondents' self-perceived level of knowledge regarding the concept of resilience. A comparison between the first question and the second, which provides only one correct answer aligned with the project's definition of resilience, indicates that the respondents' overall level of understanding of the topic is, in fact, solid. The correct answer in this case is "Ability of an industrial system to absorb and adapt to disruptions, quickly maintaining or restoring its operational functions", which differs from the others because of a more reactive perspective, instead of a more active one in terms of maintenance and efficiency.

3. Do you think the use of resilience parameters (i.e., robustness, recovery, redundancy, flexibility, etc.) is useful within the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations?

Figure 3. Question three results: perceived usefulness of resilience parameters.

From these results, it is possible to confirm the large interest towards the topic of industrial resilience, core to the RESIST project.

Question introduction: A Digital Twin (DT) represents a physical resource (object, human, system) in a virtual environment. This digital replica uses real-time data to be able to perform simulations and aid decision making.

4. Do you think the use of DTs can be an effective method to increase the resilience of industrial plants?

Figure 4. Question four results: perceived effectiveness of DTs in enhancing industrial resilience.

Despite some respondents, the majority of the voters agree to the fact that DTs can be a viable solution to work on resilience in the industrial scenario. So far, the project's underlying assumptions are fully supported by the respondents' answers.

3.2. Survey answers: Digital models for industrial systems (Section 3)

5. Do you already use or would you like to use a digital model of the productive facility/system you operate on or have academic research collaborations with to enhance its performance?

Figure 5. Question five results: current or desired use of DTs for performance enhancement.

Again, the answers given show how the digital modelling of industrial plants is very trending

6. If you use it, what are the main performance and/or KPIs that it analyzes?

Figure 6. Question six results: DTs' most used KPIs.

Between the few respondents that already use DTs of their plants, the most important KPIs that are kept track of are the ones involving energy and production, showing a strong orientation towards efficiency and cost management.

7. How important do you think it is to learn more about methods and tools to protect against attacks on production facilities/systems, including cyber, for the industrial settings in which you work or with which you have academic research collaborations?

Figure 7. Question seven results: learning importance of tools and methods to protect industrial systems from threats.

Another important RESIST research topic, that merges with resilience, is cyber-security. The answers show how high is the respondents' interest towards that kind of threats.

8. What risks/attacks do you feel are most critical in the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations?

Figure 8. Question eight results: perceived most critical risks and attacks.

8a. List here any other risks not included in the list:

Figure 9. Question eight "a" results: additional risks reported beyond the provided list.

9. Considering the most critical risks/attacks you identified in questions 8 and 8a, how much do you think the use of DT can mitigate their impact?

Figure 10. Question nine results: perceived effectiveness of DTs in mitigating critical risks and attacks.

10. What risks/attacks have you really faced or are recurring in the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations?

Figure 11. Question ten results: actual risks and attacks faced from the respondents.

This set of four questions aims to identify the risks that practitioners consider most significant and most frequently encountered, while also allowing respondents to suggest additional risks they find relevant. These contributions led to a comprehensive coverage of the potential threats to which an industrial plant may be exposed, both physical and cyber-related. Despite the wide range of identified

risks, respondents expressed strong confidence in the ability to mitigate them by leveraging the capabilities of DTs. Another insight emerges from the comparison between perceived risks and those actually encountered in practice. For certain threats such as malware/ransomware, utility interruptions, natural events, and fires, there is a relatively linear relationship between the perceived danger and the frequency with which practitioners must deal with them. In contrast, significant discrepancies appear for other types of risks. For instance, data manipulation is highly feared but rarely addressed in practice, whereas DDoS attacks are perceived as somewhat less threatening than their actual frequency of occurrence would suggest.

3.3. Survey answers: Digital models for operators/human resources (Section 4)

11. Do you think that the implementation of a DT of the human component present on the productive facility/system can have a positive impact in terms of risk reduction (both for the plant and the human component)?

Figure 12. Question eleven results: perceived impact of human DT implementation to reduce risks.

12. Do you think it is feasible to track the actions of operators/staff, limited to when engaged in high-risk operations, with a view to developing a digital model (DT) limited to internal use for process (not people) safety/performance analysis?

Figure 13. Question twelve results: tracking operator actions during high-risk operations for process safety via DTs feasibility.

Question introduction: Motion capture (or mocap) is a technology used to record human body movements and transfer them into digital form. The process involves the use of sensors or cameras that track the movements of a real actor or subject. This data is then processed to digitally represent the behavior of the physical person, from which various types of information (ergonomics, work time, etc.) can then be obtained.

13. Do you think that “mocap” technologies can be profitably applied within the industrial context in which you operate or with which you have academic research collaborations, to track the actions of operators limited to when engaged in high-risk operations, and with purposes limited to internal use for process (not people) safety/performance analyses?

Figure 14. Question thirteen results: mocap perceived applicability in industrial contexts for safety/performance analysis.

13a. List here any alternative technologies to “mocap” that are useful in achieving the same ends as set out in question 13, but which you think are better: *Optional*.

Figure 15. Question thirteen "a" results: additional technologies suggested as alternatives to mocap for tracking operator actions.

Focusing on the tracking of human actions while operating within the plant, potentially through the use of MoCap technologies and with the aim of developing a DT of the operator, this section reveals the most skeptical responses in the entire survey. While the idea of using a DT and tracking operator actions is generally well received, especially when data usage is clearly limited to operational purposes and excludes any form of misuse, concerns remain about the adoption of MoCap technology specifically.

From the authors' perspective, however, this topic remains a fundamental and central element of the RESIST project. The goal is to make the human component working within the plant an integral part of the system itself, thereby enabling a comprehensive analysis of resilience across the entire cyber-socio-technical system. The use of MoCap is intended as just one of several possible methods to achieve this integration, as also reflected in the alternative solutions suggested by the practitioners.

Question introduction: *Mixed Reality (MR) is a technology that combines elements of the real and virtual worlds, allowing them to interact in real time. Unlike augmented reality, which overlays digital content on top of the real environment, and virtual reality, which creates a fully simulated environment, MR blends both, allowing people to see and interact with digital 3-D objects as if they were present in physical space, using visors or smart glasses with motion sensors.*

14. Regardless of the investment, do you think it is technically feasible to have the possibility of being able to equip operators with MR tools (visors with holograms, smart glasses, etc.) in order to help them, thanks to the information obtainable from such tools, during the execution of potentially high-risk operations?

Figure 16. Question fourteen results: perceived technical feasibility of operators' MR tools use during high-risk operations.

According to the practitioners, the introduction of MR as an auxiliary tool to support operators' work is considered technically feasible, thereby opening up opportunities for further studies or future implementations within the project framework.

3.4. Survey answers: RESIST Guidelines (Section 5)

Question introduction: *The RESIST project uses the technologies described in the previous sections to produce “guidelines” related to industrial plant resilience and cyber-socio-technical systems modeling.*

15. Would you be interested in “guidelines” that propose resilience metrics for industrial plants, considering humans an integral part of the plant/production system?

Figure 17. Question fifteen results: interest in RESIST guidelines.

16. In what form would you like to receive/consult them?

Figure 18. Question sixteen results: preferred guidelines formats.

17. What is the main information you would like to find listed within them?

Figure 19. Question seventeen results: key informations to find on the guidelines.

The idea of developing guidelines based on RESIST project results and making them available to practitioners was positively received. Among the most requested formats for accessing such guidelines are infographics and to-do lists, as they offer a quick and intuitive approach to the topics. The main areas practitioners would like to see covered include metrics, such as indicators and benchmarks, and risk management, particularly in terms of actionable plans to follow during a crisis. Other topics considered valuable include best practices, decision-making support, and recommendations regarding technologies. The feedback gathered from these responses further confirms the alignment between the RESIST project’s objectives and practitioners’ needs. The project’s focus on providing practical tools to enhance the resilience of industrial plants, such as KPIs, best practices, and concrete actions for risk mitigation, is clearly well received.

3.5. Survey answers: Feedbacks and suggestions (Section 6)

18. Feedbacks and suggestions. *Optional.*

“Although I work in the financial services and this topic is less applicable to my case, I really believe that this project is valuable and helpful to investigate how new technologies can support industrial processes in a fast-moving environment.”

“Looks to be really interesting research”

20. Your area of employment.

Figure 20. Question twenty results: employment areas of the respondents.

21. If employed in the industry or services sectors, please add some further details (i.e. ISIC classification): *Optional*.

Figure 21. Question twenty-one results: sectors of the industry and services employed respondents.

More than half of the respondents belong to the academic sector, while the remainder represent industry practitioners. This balanced composition enriches the survey findings by bridging theoretical perspectives with practical experience, thus enhancing the relevance and applicability of the RESIST project's outputs. Among the non-academic respondents, it is noteworthy that interest in these topics extends beyond the industrial sector. Representatives from the financial and humanitarian fields also

participated in the survey, highlighting the cross-sectoral relevance and broader applicability of the project's themes.

3.6. Survey conclusions

The survey results provide encouraging confirmation of the RESIST project's relevance and direction. Respondents showed a solid understanding of the topics treated in the project, and overall feedback aligns well with the project's goals of improving industrial resilience through tools like KPIs, best practices, and risk mitigation strategies.

While some skepticism emerged around specific technologies, such as motion capture for operator tracking, there was general support for the underlying ideas, particularly when framed within a clear operational purpose. Mixed Reality was also seen as a feasible and promising solution for further applications.

The proposal to develop practical guidelines was well received, especially in accessible formats such as infographics and to-do lists. Key topics of interest included metrics, crisis response plans, and decision-making support.

The diverse background of respondents, from academia, industry, finance, and the humanitarian sector, further reinforces the cross-sectoral relevance of the project. Overall, the feedback highlights strong interest and confirms the value of the RESIST approach.

4. RESIST GUIDELINES

The following section provides a comprehensive summary of the RESIST methodology to improve industrial resilience in a cyber-socio-technical system, outlining the key steps and approaches used to analyze the case study. In addition is presented a series of open access data derived from the case study, which serves as the foundation for the subsequent analysis, as well as KPIs relevant to the study. Additionally, the chapter outlines the guidelines developed from the simulation process and the experts' survey, offering a list of implementable actions aimed at enhancing resilience from a scientific perspective but also with the important feedback of actual practitioners. This synthesis provides a general and robust framework for improving resilience in cyber-socio-technical systems.

4.1. RESIST methodology

Figure 22 introduces the RESIST methodological framework's steps: Step 1 starts with a systematic literature review to provide clarity on the integrated topics of resilience, cyber-resilience, Cyber Physical Systems (CPSs) and Cyber-Socio-Technical Systems (CSTSs) modelling. This can be brought on using scientific guidelines, i.e., the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA).

Figure 22. RESIST framework.

In the same step it is identified a relevant use case, to serve as a suitable and appropriately scaled testbed for CSTS applications within the RESIST framework. Although advancements in reliability engineering have significantly enhanced techno-centric safety management, the exploration of interactions within CSTSs remains relatively underdeveloped. To address this gap, it is developed a model based on the accident analysis methods such as Systems-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes (STAMP). The model serves as the foundation for Step 2, that is the creation of a cyber-physical digital twin (CP-DT) representing the experimental plant. Step 3 focuses on the development of a human-digital twin (H-DT) by leveraging MoCap techniques in order to understand how the operator's actions can affect the whole process. Step 4 shows how the previously developed DTs are integrated into a comprehensive Cyber-Socio-Technical System Digital Twin (CSTS-DT), enabling systemic resilience testing and analysis.

1. The first step of the RESIST framework includes a structured research process aimed at modeling the CSTS under analysis, with a particular emphasis on the theme of cyber-related failures within the industrial context. The process follows three main phases: (i) a systematic literature review establishing the theoretical foundations for the methodological approach; (ii) a preliminary descriptive analysis of the plant and its operative elements, focusing on the human operator activities; and (iii) the development of a accident analysis model (i.e., STAMP) and the application of a traditional hazard analysis method, such as System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA), to identify potential loss scenarios. The literature review aims to identify state-of-the-art modelling strategies for CSTSs, particularly in industrial environments, while addressing the increasing significance of cybersecurity. It examines how existing modelling techniques incorporate socio-technical factors and human-machine interactions to improve the safety and security of interconnected industrial systems. Based on the insights from the literature review, an accident analysis method (i.e., STAMP) is then applied to identify a set of relevant loss scenarios to be simulated in the digital environment;
2. The CP-DT is a digital representation of the CSTS under analysis, and allows to simulate and control critical system parameters such as flow rates, pressure, and levels. The CP-DT is composed of multiple subsystems, each responsible for simulating different physical processes like fluid flow and pressure regulation. These subsystems interact dynamically to maintain desired operating conditions. The DT relies on predictive modeling, where system variables (i.e., pressure, flow) are used to forecast future states, enabling real-time optimization of performance.

By modeling these interactions, the system adjusts control actions based on current conditions, ensuring stability and efficiency. To reach this result a control strategy is adopted, aiming to regulate critical parameters within optimal limits, while feedback control mechanisms, typically using PID controllers, adjusts system variables like valve settings to maintain balance. Given the interdependencies between parameters (e.g., changes in pressure affect flow), the controllers must operate in a coordinated manner to avoid destabilizing the system. Synchronization between subsystems is critical for achieving consistent and stable operation, that is why real-time model updates are incorporated through techniques like Kalman filtering and machine learning. These filters help reduce uncertainty in system predictions, even when sensor data is incomplete or unreliable. Additionally, machine learning algorithms refine the system's predictive capabilities by learning from historical data and adapting to changing operating conditions over time. The DT architecture also supports the simulation of cyber-attacks, enabling the identification of vulnerabilities and the testing of system resilience. By simulating the impact of cyber disruptions on the subsystems, the system can evaluate how such attacks affect the system's performance. This simulation is crucial for understanding the potential consequences of cyber threats and developing strategies to mitigate their impact on the system;

3. The development of the H-DT starts with the selection of a suitable MoCap technology, considering the quality of the recording needed, the spatial area of work and the type of enabling technology (i.e., inertial, optical). After choosing the right technology, a series of on-site recordings of the operator's work are brought on to collect reliable datasets representing the operator's performance on the plant. The collected data can be converted to other formats, to enable some useful processing: by using the concept of Control Volumes, solid geometric figures of any dimension and shape that can be positioned anywhere within the plant's layout, it is possible to pair a physical area or equipment to a digital one to lend significance to the position of the operator over time. Each CV is defined by its own name, position and dimensions in the 3D space. By using a script, it is possible to check if the operator is actively working inside a CV for each frame of the recorded operative datasets by comparing the positions of said CVs and the operator's. Thanks to this, it is possible to extract some important parameters regarding the operators' performance, such as the cumulative time spent by the operator inside each CV, the sequence of CVs visited during the scenario with the time of each visit, and the distance over time between the operator and the CVs.
4. From a hardware-software integration perspective, the system architecture comprises two interconnected DTs: one for the physical plant and another for modeling the operator's behavior. These two components need to be linked via a dedicated integration layer that enables efficient data exchange and coordination. The CP-DT simulates system dynamics and exposes essential process variables. Upon the occurrence of specific predefined conditions, it sends signals to the H-DT, which initiates a simulated decision-making process. The operator model interprets the information, assesses the context, and returns suitable control actions. These responses are then relayed back to the CP-DT, influencing its behavior in real time. The integration layer maintains synchronization between the two models, ensuring coherent and adaptive interaction across various operational scenarios. The integrated simulation process unfolds through a series of interconnected stages that gradually build a realistic and dynamic representation of the plant's operations and the operator's behavior. The process begins with the recreation of the digital

scenario that mirrors the plant's functioning as described earlier. From this scenario, disruptive events are simulated, leading to an underperformance of the system. Concurrently, the data regarding the operator's behavior is extracted randomly from one of the simulations, defining the time needed to complete the anomaly detection phase, the shutdown and the restart phase.

4.2. RESIST open access data

Below are provided the links to access the open-access datasets generated during the project. These datasets are accompanied by detailed explanations of how the data were collected and guidance on how they can be reused for independent simulations.

4.2.1 Plant open access data

In the energy sector, and particularly in the oil and gas supply chain, the management of complex plants operating under extreme conditions demands increasing attention to safety, efficiency, and resilience. To meet these challenges, the use of digital models, such as digital twins, and artificial intelligence algorithms is playing an increasingly important role. However, without reliable experimental data, these technologies remain ineffective or, worse, potentially misleading. The dataset collected from the experimental plant simulating an oil and gas transportation system represents a valuable resource for multiple application areas, far beyond its original purpose. Its rich and detailed structure, which includes both normal operating conditions and anomalies of varying severity, makes it a highly versatile tool for research and innovation in the industrial domain.

- **Development of predictive maintenance algorithms:** One of the main applications is the training and validation of predictive maintenance models. The dataset includes clear and progressive signals related to degraded conditions, such as simulated obstructions or leaks, enabling the identification of early fault patterns. This supports the creation of algorithms capable of anticipating failures before they become critical, reducing downtime and optimizing maintenance strategies.
- **Automatic anomaly detection:** The variety and control of introduced anomalies allow testing and benchmarking of both supervised and unsupervised anomaly detection techniques. The availability of precisely labeled data (type and severity of anomaly) is a key advantage that enables the evaluation of model performance in borderline situations, enhancing their generalization capabilities.
- **Design and validation of digital twins:** The dataset provides all the information needed to digitally replicate the plant's behavior. With data on sensors, pneumatic valves, PID controllers, and setpoints, it is possible to develop realistic digital twins to test hypothetical scenarios, control strategies, and perturbation effects without physical risks.

- ***Study of multiphase system dynamics:*** Since the plant handles a mixture of two fluids with different properties, air and water, the data are ideal for analyzing typical multiphase flow phenomena such as transients, flow instabilities, or phase separation. This has practical implications not only for the oil & gas industry but also for chemical, pharmaceutical, and food processing sectors.
- ***Engineering education and training:*** Finally, the dataset has significant educational value. It can be used to introduce operators to topics such as industrial control, process simulation, applied machine learning, and anomaly management. The inclusion of JSON files, plots, and thorough documentation encourages active and interdisciplinary learning.

All raw data are publicly available on the Zenodo platform with identification number 10.5281/zenodo.15977126 and can be directly accessed at the following URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/15977126>. This open access ensures that the dataset is freely available for further research, replication of results, and validation of methodologies described in this work.

4.2.2 *Operator open access data*

The operator open access data provided in this study includes, first and foremost, a collection of isolated recordings of basic actions performed by the operator. These actions were captured using motion capture technology in a controlled and safe laboratory environment. The action segments represent elementary movements or routine tasks typically carried out during plant operations, for example, taking a step forward, kneeling, executing a shutdown from the control room, or inspecting a sensor. The data are structured in tabular form: in the sheet named as the file, each row corresponds to a frame and includes, in order, the frame number, timestamp, and the (x, y, z) coordinate triplets for each sensor. Sensor names are listed in the header for ease of identification. This structure enables continuous spatial tracking of the operator throughout the duration of the recordings. As for “Sheet1” in each file, here the data represent the “deltas”, namely the variation in terms of position between two consecutive frames for each coordinate of each sensor. In this way, it is possible to define how each sensor moves over time, drawing a “trajectory” that identifies each basic action’s movement and enabling the concatenation between actions.

All collected data were post-processed using a Hampel Filter (a generalization of the median filter) capable of effectively identifying and removing outliers. On average, the proportion of detected outliers was approximately 3% for each recording. The cleaned data were then imported into Microsoft Excel to ensure compatibility and readability across multiple platforms, including MATLAB, which was used for the subsequent analyses.

By concatenating the basic actions recordings, it is possible to reconstruct complete operative scenarios. This modular approach allows for flexible simulation of different workflows by assembling sequences of basic actions, provided the layout of the plant and the relevant points of interest are known. Such flexibility supports the creation of fully digital yet realistic operator routines for further analysis or testing.

In addition, the provided data also includes full recordings of real operational scenarios captured directly on field using the same motion capture technology. For each scenario, five repetitions were performed, along with three additional recordings in which the plant shutdown was carried out from the control panel rather than the control room, as is typically the case.

By selecting specific sensors of interest (i.e., those located on the pelvis), it is possible to analyze, frame by frame, the operator's relative position with respect to predefined reference points within the facility. This analysis was conducted using the concept of control volumes (CVs), three-dimensional geometric shapes representing areas or pieces of equipment within the plant. A custom script was developed to compare, at each time step, the position of the selected sensors with the defined control volumes. This enables reconstruction of the operator's sequence of interactions with various components of the plant, as well as computing the times spent in each visit. The modularity of this approach ensures that simulations can be easily adapted by modifying the coordinates of the control volumes to reflect different configurations or analytical needs.

All raw data are publicly available on the Zenodo platform with identification number 10.5281/zenodo.16634663 and can be directly accessed at the following URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/16634663>. This open access ensures that the dataset is freely available for further research, replication of results, and validation of methodologies described in this work.

4.3. RESIST KPIs

The fundamental KPI derived from the RESIST project focus on the quantification of system resilience in the face of cyber-physical disruptions, with explicit consideration of human operator behavior. Central to this analysis is the integrated performance profile, which combines plant process data with motion-captured operator responses to simulate realistic intervention scenarios. From these profiles, detection delay, intervention latency, and recovery duration represent the main KPIs extracted (defined in D6000-A). These temporal metrics provide a structured means to evaluate how promptly and effectively operators can identify and mitigate cyber-induced anomalies. Furthermore, a comparative area-based metric was adopted to quantify resilience, defined as the ratio between the area under the curve of nominal plant operation and that of the degraded state following a cyber incident (as presented in D6000-A). This approach captures not only the severity and duration of disruptions but also the extent to which operator actions influence the plant's return to steady-state conditions. Collectively, these metrics offer a robust framework for assessing the impact of human-in-the-loop performance on system-level resilience and can support the development of operator training programs, interface design improvements, and decision-support systems in cyber-socio-technical environments.

4.4. RESIST redesign actions implementation

Following the multi-scenario simulations conducted in WP5000, which defined a set of redesign actions from the authors' side, the survey results presented above now allow for a meaningful comparison with the needs expressed by practitioners. This section lists the redesign actions by implementation order, to support the resilience improvement process.

Figure 23. Redesign actions implementation pyramid.

Figure 23 shows the redesign actions implementation pyramid: the chart visually organizes the redesign actions, highlighting their implementation priorities from the base to the apex strategic layers. Note that each redesign action is fully detailed in deliverable D6000A. The actions are prioritized following the survey results, which highlighted a strong need in facing malware/ransomware attacks, utility interruption and industrial risks such as failures. For this reason, at the base of the pyramid, the actions focus on foundational system improvements. These include Sensor redundancy, which aims to mitigate the impact of sensor failures by introducing redundant sensors or data fusion techniques, and Valve control strategy optimization, which seeks to improve the balance between inlet and outlet valve flows. Additionally, Novice operators interface support is designed to aid less experienced operators by enhancing the interface to reflect the decision-making processes of expert operators, while Patterns redesign simplifies operator tasks during inspections, and Mocap Equipment Alternatives explore alternative technologies for operator data collection.

In the middle of the pyramid, the actions focus on improving system functionality and operator preparedness. Functional segmentation for anomaly containment introduces modular plant segmentation to prevent anomalies from propagating, while Training for resilience and adaptability aims to reduce response variability in operators by providing targeted crisis-management training. The integration of AI is positioned here as well, enhancing crisis management through real-time monitoring, anomaly detection, and decision support.

At the apex of the pyramid, the most impactful and forward-looking action is the implementation of a Parallel Digital Twin for security. This action aims to provide a robust layer of security by creating an isolated predictive model of the plant that can detect anomalies and isolate the system from potential cyber threats, enhancing resilience against such risks. Lastly, the Crisis management protocols ensure that operators, regardless of experience level, have a structured, comprehensive protocol to guide their actions during a crisis, synthesizing critical information for effective decision-making.

These actions collectively form a comprehensive strategy to improve system resilience and address the key risk factors highlighted in the survey, supporting the goal of enhancing operational stability, safety, and security in the face of increasing industrial complexity and cyber threats by increasing the system's resilience.

The survey results also indicated that the most appreciated formats for accessing information about the guidelines are infographics and to-do lists. As illustrative examples, one version of each format is presented here for two of the redesign actions.

In general, key elements to consider when developing infographics include:

- A clear and concise visual hierarchy;
- Minimal text supported by icons or visuals;
- Logical flow of information (i.e., timeline, process, or step-by-step structure);
- Use of color coding to distinguish categories or steps;
- Consistency in design and labeling;
- Inclusion of key takeaways or actionable points.

Figure 24 shows a hypothetical infographic for sensor redundancy implementation.

Sensor Redundancy

Sensor failure: the failure or compromise of a single sensor can significantly affect the entire system

Redundant sensors: incorporating redundant sensors capable of estimating critical parameters

Data fusion: implement techniques to infer missing or corrupted data

Figure 24. Sensor redundancy infographic.

As for to-do lists, essential components typically are:

- Actionable, specific tasks broken down into manageable steps;
- Prioritization or sequencing of tasks (i.e., must-do, should-do);
- Estimated time or deadlines, when applicable;
- Responsible roles or stakeholders (if relevant);
- Checkboxes or indicators for progress tracking;
- Alignment with the guideline's objectives or expected outcomes.

Following here, it is proposed a to-do list to select and implement MoCap alternatives:

1. Assess Current System Requirements

- Define the target application
- Document current performance metrics (i.e., capture frequency, range, latency, accuracy)
- Identify current system limitations and weak points

2. Research Available MoCap Technologies

- Review existing technologies (i.e., optical, inertial, magnetic, markerless, hybrid)
- Compare performance parameters:

- Capture frequency
 - Operational range
 - Environmental sensitivity (i.e., lighting, occlusion)
 - Latency and data processing needs
 - Evaluate software and integration requirements
3. Perform Technical Feasibility Study
- Test selected systems in controlled conditions
 - Analyze compatibility with current hardware/software infrastructure
 - Assess scalability and future-proofing potential
4. Engage Stakeholders
- Gather feedback from end users (researchers, technicians, performers)
 - Consider ergonomics, wearability, and training needs
 - Evaluate compliance with institutional and safety standards
5. Conduct Cost–Benefit Analysis
- Analyze initial investment and maintenance costs
 - Estimate expected improvements in data quality and workflow
 - Compare long-term value versus current setup
6. Plan Integration and Deployment
- Develop implementation timeline and milestones
 - Schedule training for operators and analysts
7. Monitor and Optimize Post-Deployment
- Establish feedback loops for continuous improvement
 - Document performance metrics before and after transition
 - Adjust workflows and parameters as needed

5. CONCLUSION

The survey results provide compelling evidence supporting the relevance and strategic direction of the RESIST project. Respondents demonstrated a strong understanding of the topics addressed in the project, and the overall feedback aligns well with the project's objectives of enhancing industrial resilience. While some skepticism was expressed regarding specific technologies, such as motion capture for operator tracking, there was general support for the underlying concepts, particularly when framed with a clear operational purpose. The proposal to develop practical guidelines was well received. The areas of greatest interest to include are the definition of metrics, crisis response planning and decision-making support. The diverse background of respondents, spanning academia, industry, finance, and the humanitarian sector, further underscores the cross-sectoral relevance of the project.

The final handbook (RESIST guidelines), developed based on these findings, details the methodology employed, with a focus on the construction of the two standalone Digital Twins (CP-DT and H-DT) and their integration within the simulation process. The handbook provides open access data on the simulations conducted to assess operational resilience, highlighting the key KPIs to monitor. Furthermore, it outlines redesign actions, derived from both scientific contributions and the needs identified through the survey, thereby bridging theoretical foundations with practical considerations.

This relatively novel hybrid approach aims to provide a more holistic and practical framework for achieving the goals of the RESIST project.

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